

Ho Chi Minh's Ideology on Promoting the Human Factor and Apply in Vietnam Today

Nguyen Minh Tri, DinhThe Hoang, Nguyen Van Bung

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Abstract

Promoting the human factor plays a particularly important role, being the driving force in promoting the socio-economic development of each country in this era. Therefore, most countries in the world, including Vietnam, consider investment in human development as the goal of their development strategy. Ho Chi Minh's ideology on man and promoting the human factor is a comprehensive, various and profound system of views, occupying a central position in his entire thought. The noble purpose and the whole life of Ho Chi Minh's revolutionary activities are class liberation, national liberation and human liberation. This is the inheritance and creative development of ideas about people in the national and human cultural treasures in general and Marxism-Leninism in particular.

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Introduction

Ho Chi Minh's ideology on man and promoting the human factor is a comprehensive, various and profound system of views, occupying a central position in his entire thought. Promoting the human factor is the goal and driving force for the socio-economic development of each country in today's era. Therefore, most countries in the world, including Vietnam, consider investment in human development as the goal of their development strategy. Ho Chi Minh left our Party and nation an invaluable theoretical legacy on particularly important and fundamental issues of the Vietnamese revolution, including profound philosophical thoughts on construction and innovate human, so far still have the same theoretical and practical value.

During his life of revolutionary activities, Ho Chi Minh always considered the human issue as the most sacred and noble goal. That goal has become an ideal, shining in his every thought, gesture, and action. Although there is no work specifically discussing the human being, the thought on promoting the human factor has been expressed in a diverse and rich manner, becoming a cross-cutting thought in the entire Ho Chi Minh system of thought. Implementing his thought, the revolutionary cause in our country in general, the process of fighting for and maintaining the independence and freedom of the Fatherland in particular have been bringing into full play the human factor, thereby, affirming the bravery, intelligence, soul and strength of Vietnamese people. Two research questions are revealed as following:

- What are the contents of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on promoting the human factor in the nation's revolutionary cause?
- How is the application of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on promoting the human factor in the struggle for and keeping the independence and freedom of the Fatherland in Vietnam today?

Research Methods

Method and Data

The paper's approach is based on the worldview and the methodology of Marxist philosophy, and at the same time uses specific research methods such as analysis and synthesis, logic and history, inductive and interpretation, abstraction, generalization, comparison, comparison and literary methods for research and presentation.

Research results

Ho Chi Minh's ideology on promoting the human factor in the nation's revolutionary cause

Inheriting the quintessence of national and human cultural ideology, absorbing, applying and developing creatively Marxist-Leninist doctrines, Ho Chi Minh raised his thoughts on man to a new height and formed Ho Chi Minh's humanism. His thought on promoting the human factor is reflected in many speeches and articles

and is reflected in the practice of directing the Vietnamese revolution, in which, the following main contents emerge:

Firstly, people are the most precious capital, the great driving force, the decisive factor in the victory of the Vietnamese revolution.

Ho Chi Minh did not use the term “human factor”, but often used phrases such as “people's power”, “people's talents”, and “people's force”. However, in Ho Chi Minh's mind, he always had a high opinion of the role of the human factor in the Vietnamese revolution. He mentioned the human factor at three levels: People in general; workers, farmers, intellectuals, soldiers, cadres and each specific person - that is, the working people (except reactionaries). He once affirmed: “The word “people”, in a narrow sense, means family, brothers, relatives, companions. In a broad sense, it means compatriots in the whole country. In a broader sense, it means human” (Ho, 2011, Vol 6, p.130). The role of man is the role of the masses, the true creator of history, not “some heroic individuals”. According to him, “there is nothing in the sky as precious as the people”; “power and force reside in the people” (Ho, 2011, Vol 6, p.130), the people are always placed in the highest position, the position of mastery in the most important issues of the revolution and society. The people are both masters, but the people are at the same time doing the work of mastering, being both the subject and the object, and the force, the driving force and the goal of the Vietnamese revolution.

The cause of the struggle for national liberation, national reunification, building a new life, and moving towards socialism must all start from people, from promoting the human factor. According to him, a very simple reason to understand is that everything is done by people, material wealth in society is made by workers and farmers; thanks to the labor of workers and farmers, society is constantly developing. He explained the scientific basis for that role comes from the following: “With the population, no matter how big or difficult the job, it can be done. Nothing can not be done. People know how to solve many problems in a simple, quick and complete way, which talented people and large organizations can't think of” (Ho, 2011, Vol 5, p. 335).

People are the great and decisive driving force for all victories of the Vietnamese revolution. In his mind, “the people are the most precious capital, having the people means having everything. Even though the problem is 10 times easier, without the help of the people, that problem is still difficult to solve” (Ho, 2011, Vol15, p. 280), the human factor is the most important resource, the resource of all resources. At the same time, President Ho Chi Minh always considered people as the goal of the revolutionary cause. However, he always pays attention to the goal achieved in each specific condition and situation. Before taking power, the highest goal of the revolutionary cause was national independence and national liberation. After taking power, on January 10, 1946, at a meeting of the Committee for Research on the National Construction Plan, Ho Chi Minh asked to immediately implement: “Make the people have food. Make people have clothes to wear. Make people have a place to live. Make the people educated” (Ho, 2011, Vol 4, p. 175). When the North went into economic recovery and completed land reform, Ho Chi Minh insisted on “gradually raising the people's living standards... while reducing the contribution of farmers”. In the context of focusing on armed struggle to liberate the South, at the Conference of the Politburo, on July 30, 1962, Ho Chi Minh asked the question: What should we do, if necessary, we can reduce a part of construction, in order to better solve the problem of food and clothing of the masses, do not let people's lives become too stressful. The human issue is very important. The factory also needs more than people, the excitement of the masses. Do everything for people, make the masses understand socialism better. When the resistance war against the US entered a drastic phase, the goal of “nothing is more precious than independence and freedom” was at the high level of the national value ladder. Human goals are closely linked to national sovereignty. At the third session of the National Assembly, on April 10, 1965, Ho Chi Minh called upon the people: At this time, fighting the US and saving the country is the most sacred task of all Vietnamese patriots. In December 1965, speaking at the closing session of the 12th Conference, the third term of the Party Central Committee, he asked to take great care of the people's lives, especially the lives of the children, families of war invalids and martyrs, people's lives in heavily bombarded areas, and low-income families with many children. And in number 1 of the newspaper People in Need, he stated that his goal was to liberate people, then in the Testament, he also mentioned that the first job was for people. Thus, he took the “immutability” which is all for the sake of man to respond to the “multi-unexpected changes” of historical conditions. The common goal is to liberate people from oppression and exploitation, to live happily and freely, but it must depend on specific conditions to progress step by step.

Secondly, promoting the human factor as a unity between qualities and capabilities.

According to Ho Chi Minh, in order to successfully carry out the great revolutionary cause but full of hardships and difficulties, so the promoting the qualities (virtue) and capacity (talent) of each person played a decisive role. Appreciating the role of virtue and talent, however, he did not separate these two factors but put them in a dialectical relationship, in which morality was considered the root and foundation of the revolutionary and the people in general. However, he did not absolutize the role of morality or debase, separate from talent, but “virtue” is always associated with “talent”. It's better to have both virtue and talent; the greater the talent, the higher the virtue; “virtue – talent” are intertwined in the personality of the revolutionary. However, morality is

the basis and condition for promoting and developing the revolutionary's talents. He pointed out, "having talent without virtue... not only can't do anything useful for society, but it's also harmful to society. If there is virtue but no talent, it is like the Buddha who does no harm, but also does no good to mankind" (Ho, 2011, Vol 11, p.399). Therefore, Ho Chi Minh demanded that each cadre and party member, along with noble revolutionary qualities, also have to be capable, because it is only when they have the ability to fulfill their assigned tasks. To build socialism, first of all, there must be socialist people, who are passionately patriotic, ethically pure and excellent in talent, and have both political integrity and professional competence.

Thirdly, in order to promote the human factor, and must know how to use people.

During his entire active life, as the head of the Party and State, Ho Chi Minh established the basic views on using people, using and promoting the human factor with a truly revolutionary spirit science. Even in the extremely difficult early years of the revolutionary government, he wrote a series of articles on this issue such as: "About the reception of representatives of the unions"; "Letter to comrades in the province"; "Lack of organization - a major defect in People's Committees"; "Talent and national construction"; "Correcting the way we work". In the article "Finding talented people" dated November 20, 1946, with very sincere and respectful words, he wrote: "Construction requires talented people. Among the 20 million compatriots, there is certainly no shortage of talented people. I'm afraid because the Government can't hear it, see it everywhere, so that talented people can't come from... Now I want to correct that, and honor the talented people" (Ho, 2011, Vol 4, p.504). According to him, using people is essentially promoting all the potentials of the human factor in order to create synergy for the great national unity bloc to solve revolutionary tasks. The goal of using people is to achieve "Human Peace". Therefore, the use of people is not limited to certain classes and groups, but to all people: men, women, old people, young people, girls, boys, regardless of religion, party, ethnicity. Not only people in the Viet Minh's Party, but also many talented people outside, even those who left for enemy-occupied zones, we did not despise them, but had to help them make progress, let them work with us" (Ho, 2011, Vol 9, p. 47).

Ho Chi Minh advocated and promoted the human factor on the basis of using talented people. Talented people or talents are understood in the broadest sense: "big talent, small talent"; "reputable people", "people with justice, loyalty, zeal for the interests of the Fatherland and people", "talented people", "sage", "good people" but have in common purpose "for the interests of the Fatherland, the interests of the compatriots". Especially, according to him, honoring people must be right and skillfully; there is a close relationship between right and skillfully, right and wrong, the results will be limited, being clever but not right, it will definitely fail, sometimes even damage "people". It is true that the first basic requirement, because if it is correct, it will be shown well, choosing the right person is the essence of using people, is a science. Cleverness must ensure to lead to the right, the objective, skillful is an art. He also emphasized the use of talents outside the Party, skillfully combining young cadres with old cadres, fair rewards and punishments, and must know how to use a team of capable people to work for the common good, not must side, gather around themselves the flatterers, the opportunists.

Fourthly, measures to promote the human factor

To promote the human factor requires the Party, the Government and each individual to have a correct awareness of the position and role of the human factor; must have infinite love, sympathy, absolute trust in people, the will to fight for human liberation. President Ho Chi Minh emphasized: "Understanding Marxism - Leninism is to live with meaningful love" (Ho, 2011, Vol 15, p. 668). According to him, people in the world are not the Gods, no one is immune from defects, so they must be skillful in enhancing their good and correcting their bad. Sympathy, forgiveness, generosity, tolerance... have formed Ho Chi Minh's tolerance, but the greatest tolerance can be listening, respecting the opinions and ideas of others, not taking own opinions and thoughts to impose, refute or exclude other people's opinions and ideas. At the same time, each cadre and party member "must first believe that the people's strength and wisdom are infinite" (Ho, 2011, Vol 12, p. 283), from deeds, words to the way of living, how to make the people believe, the people obey, the people love. Infinite love, sympathy, absolute trust in people, determination to strive for human liberation become the first premise to be able to promote and mobilize the human factor.

In order to promote the human factor, Ho Chi Minh, together with the Party and Government, planned and established a relatively complete system of policies, in line with reality, serving the interests of the nation, freedom, comfortable lives and happiness of the people, covering all areas of social life, especially social security issues. In economics, Ho Chi Minh emphasized the policy of production development and reasonable wages. In terms of society, it is necessary to implement a system of social policies towards people, harmoniously resolving the relationship between individual and collective interests, between private interests and common interests.

To form the right motives and purposes for people in activities, it is necessary to promote policies for advocacy, propaganda and education. Ho Chi Minh affirmed: In order for the people to believe, follow, and support, in order for the human factor to be promoted, attention must be paid to the people's material and spiritual life, and human rights must be protected. The most important premise for these rights to be protected is recognized in the Constitution and laws. There is a constitution and a law, but the basic thing according to Ho Chi Minh is to realize it through campaigns and revolutionary movements to ensure democratic rights, because "practicing

democracy is the universal key which can solve all difficulties” (Ho, 2011, Vol 15, p. 325), only by promoting democracy to a high degree can all forces of the people be mobilized to move the revolution forward. Ho Chi Minh reminded: The Party needs to take care of educating them in revolutionary morality, training them to become heirs to build socialism with both “political integrity and professional competence”. Ho Chi Minh considered building a contingent of cadres and party members to be concerned first of all with the cause of growing people because “cadres are the root of work”. In addition, he was constantly interested in the education and training of the young generation, the future owner of the country.

Thus, the issue of promoting the human factor was mentioned by Ho Chi Minh with profound, comprehensive and scientific content. He affirmed, the human factor is the most precious capital, the great driving force, the decisive factor for the victory of the Vietnamese revolution; People are the most precious capital, having people is having everything, so we have to start from the human factor, for people, for people and came back to people. At the same time, he also pointed out a system of comprehensive solutions, considering the correct implementation of those solutions as a key step, determining success in the problem of promoting the human factor in the revolutionary cause of the country.

The application of Ho Chi Minh's ideology on promoting the human factor in the struggle for and keeping the independence and freedom of the Fatherland

Creatively applying the thought of President Ho Chi Minh, in the process of leading the revolution, our Party always considers human resources as “the main resource of all resources”, the most important endogenous resource that determines the success of the national construction and defense. Not only affirming the role of people and the strength of the great national unity bloc in the struggle for independence and freedom, our Party has implemented many undertakings and policies to arouse and promote the strength of the country in reality. Thanks to that, in the two resistance wars against the French colonialists and the American imperialists, despite their poor and backward economic and military potential, they aroused the will and energy of the Vietnamese people; “the entire Vietnamese people are determined to put all their spirit and force, life and wealth to uphold that freedom and independence” as one million people stood up to defeat the invasion of the French colonial empire and the American empire, completely liberated the country, unified the country, and moved up to socialism. As President Ho Chi Minh summed up: “Our history teaches us this lesson: When our people unite as one, our country is independent and free. On the contrary, whenever our people are not united, they are invaded by foreign countries” (Ho, 2011, Vol 3, p.256).

Entering the period of national construction and defense, in order to maintain the independence and freedom of the Fatherland, our Party has focused on “promoting the creativity of all strata of the people, directing that creativity to the cause of building a new society” (Communist Party of Vietnam, 1987, p. 9). All undertakings and policies of the Party focus on fostering and promoting the human factor on the basis of ensuring fairness and equality in the rights and obligations of citizens; bring into play all the potentials and strengths of people in order to both focus highly on economic development and strengthen national defense and security, creating a solid foundation to protect the achievements of independence and freedom in the new conditions. At the 4th Plenum of the Central Committee, emphasized: “Human beings are the most precious capital, taking care of people's happiness is the highest goal of our regime... We need to deeply understand the issues of human rights. The great value and decisive significance of the human factor, the subject of all creation, all sources of material and cultural wealth, all civilizations of nations, must come from the human spirit profoundly aimed at comprehensive human development, building a just and compassionate society, establishing really good and progressive relations between people and people in production and in life” (Communist Party of Vietnam, 1993, p.5). The Ninth Congress of the Party affirmed: Our society is a society for people and people always hold the central position of economic and social development, “development of education and training is one of the important driving force for the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country, a condition for promoting human resources, a fundamental factor for social development and rapid and sustainable economic growth”(Vietnamese Communist Party, 2001, p. 108 - 109).

Consistent with the strategic thought on human development in the renovation period, the Resolution of the 11th Party Congress continues to affirm that people are the center of the development strategy and at the same time the development subject. Developing and improving the quality of human resources, especially high-quality human resources, is a strategic breakthrough, a decisive factor in accelerating the development and application of science and technology, and restructuring the economy, transforming the growth model and the most important competitive advantage to ensure fast, effective and sustainable development (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2011, p. 130). At the 12th National Congress, the issue of “comprehensive human development” was identified by our Party as one of the general tasks of national development in the five years from 2016 to 2020 and “developing the Vietnamese people comprehensively must become an objective of the development strategy” (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016, p. 126). This is a step forward in the Party's awareness after 30 years of renovation, affirming and emphasizing the particularly important role of promoting the human factor, developing comprehensively, meeting the requirements of the national construction and defense in the period of international integration.

Realizing the views and policies of our Party and State, after more than 35 years of renovation, Vietnam has achieved important human development achievements that are highly appreciated by the international community. The renovation process always comes from the interests of the people, relies on the people, and promotes the active and creative role of the people, so it has won great achievements of historical significance. From a poor and backward agricultural country, Vietnam has now escaped from underdevelopment and become a middle-income country; socio-economic development has progressed; people's life in all aspects has been significantly improved; Society and politics are stabilized; national defense and security are strengthened, national sovereignty is maintained; The position and power of the country is increasingly enhanced;... These achievements have both demonstrated the great strength of the Vietnamese people and affirmed the value of independence and freedom; at the same time, creating the most solid foundation for maintaining the independence and freedom of the Fatherland.

Currently, besides the advantages, the cause of national defense is facing many difficulties and challenges. The situation in the world and the region continues to be complicated and unpredictable, with many potential destabilizing factors. The modern scientific and technological revolution and the globalization trend have had a strong impact on all areas of life, posing many new problems that need to be resolved in the protection of independence and sovereignty. In the country, besides the great achievements achieved in the renovation years, there are also many shortcomings and limitations. In particular, deterioration in political thought, morality and lifestyle of a large number of cadres and party members has not yet been pushed back, and some parts are more sophisticated and complicated; corruption, wastefulness and negativity are still serious, focusing on the number of party members holding positions in the state apparatus. Many party organizations and members are still limited in awareness, neglectful, lethargic, confused in identifying and fighting, preventing "self-evolution", "self-transformation" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016, pp. 22 - 23). Enemy and reactionary forces have strengthened the implementation of the strategy of "peaceful evolution" against sabotaging our country's revolution by sophisticated and dangerous tricks, especially by thoroughly using the media on the internet to prevent; Disputes at Sea.

Faced with these difficulties and challenges, it is necessary to continue to creatively apply Ho Chi Minh's thought on promoting the human factor, awakening and promoting all resources and creative potentials of the people, creating strength for the people general strength to maintain and promote the values of independence and freedom. To do that, it is necessary to focus on implementing the following key solutions:

Firstly, comprehensively develop Vietnamese people to meet the requirements of the cause of national construction and defense in the period of international integration. It is necessary to build a standard value system of Vietnamese people, "... summarizing... the standard value system of Vietnamese people in the period of industrialization, modernization and international integration" on the core issues: "... personality, morality, intelligence, creative capacity, physical body, soul, social responsibility, civic duty, sense of law observance" (Communist Party Vietnam, 2016, p. 127), creating an environment and conditions for each person to self-practice and strive for maturity. Focus on developing Vietnamese people with basic characteristics: patriotism, compassion, love, honesty, solidarity, industriousness, creativity. Promote fundamental and comprehensive reform of education and training, improve the quality of human resources, improve intellectual capacity and foster knowledge for Vietnamese people to meet the requirements of innovation and international integration of the Vietnamese knowledge economy and learning society. Improving the physical strength and stature of the Vietnamese person, linking physical education with education on knowledge, morality and life skills, meeting the requirements of national construction and defense. Building and promoting the lifestyle "One for all and all for one"; forming a lifestyle with a sense of self-respect and self-control, living and working in accordance with the Constitution and laws, and protecting the environment; harmonious combination of personal positivity and social positivity; promote personal responsibility towards self, family and society. In particular, it is necessary to associate cultural development with perfecting the Vietnamese people; strengthen art education, improve people's aesthetic perception capacity, especially youth; promote the role of literature - art in fostering people's souls and emotions; ensure the right to enjoy and create culture of each citizen and community. Criticism fight repels evils, backwardness; fights against wrong and negative views and behaviors that adversely affect the construction of Vietnamese culture and people.

Secondly, take care of building an environment that honors traditional and historical cultural values. It is necessary to focus on educating the nation's history of nation building and defense, our people's tradition of resilient and indomitable struggle, spreading the word about heroes, martyrs, and typical patriotic examples, make each person, especially each young person, proud of the nation's traditions and history, look into the typical examples in society, realize their responsibilities to the Fatherland, family and society. In order to do that, first of all, it is necessary to actively promote the process of teaching history, vividly reproducing important historical events; combine many information channels providing historical knowledge, especially books, newspapers, pictures, documents, movies, music, etc. Widely use various forms such as: seminars, thematic activities, forums, research contests, propaganda, praising good people and good deeds to foster patriotism, self-reliance, self-reliance, arousing dreams and great ambitions for young people.

It is necessary to arouse and promote the value of historical vestiges. The war has receded, but in all parts of the country, there are still resounding heart-wrenching stories about “Legendary” lands and people. Still there Dien Bien Phu, Con Dao, Phu Quoc, Truong Son, Quang Tri Ancient Citadel, thousands of cemeteries and memorials for heroes and martyrs or millions of wounded and sick soldiers, Heroic Mothers, families with meritorious services to the revolution, etc. Across all regions of the country and in each life contains fierce memories, soaked in blood and tears, but shining with revolutionary heroism. Therefore, it is necessary to increase activities to visit historical monuments and museums; organize traditional exchanges and talks for the younger generation to learn about stories, lives, real people, and real things.

Moreover, traditional and historical education needs to take place right in the life of the family, school and society. Each force, each organization needs to have specific jobs and actions to express pride in the nation's history, honor those who have sacrificed their lives for the country. Closely combine standard building moral standards, a typical example with “anti” all expressions and behaviors contrary to national morality and traditions; attach importance to education and training through practical activities and patriotic emulation movements, making each person capable of self-resistance and actively fighting against the plots of “peaceful evolution” of hostile forces.

Thirdly, promote socio-economic development, improve people's life in all aspects; consolidate and strengthen the great national unity bloc. Socio-economic development, taking care of building a great national unity block will create conditions to promote the human factor, creating a solid foundation to protect the independence and freedom of the Fatherland. Therefore, it is necessary to promote economic development on the basis of effectively exploiting the potential and strengths of each region, along with protecting the ecological environment. Mobilize all resources to create breakthroughs in hunger eradication and poverty reduction, production development, care for spiritual life, preservation and promotion of cultural identities of ethnic groups, improvement of people's intellectual level, training and attracting high-quality human resources, step by step solving social problems. Prioritize resources to create changes in socio-economic development in remote and isolated areas, ethnic minority areas and strategic areas. Regularly take care of building and strengthening the great national unity bloc, thoroughly grasping and implementing the viewpoint of maintaining independence, freedom, and reunification of the Fatherland, realizing the Wealthy people, strong country, just and civilized society as a common ground for national unity. Regularly settle harmoniously the relationship of interests between classes and social forces; well implement grassroots democracy, respect the people, resolutely fight against bureaucracy, corruption, violations of the people's mastery, and activities that divide and sabotage the great national unity bloc.

Fourthly, firmly consolidate the all-people defense and people's security, build a strong and comprehensive people's armed forces with high combat power. Strengthening the national defense - security potential, attaching importance to building political potential, the posture of the people's hearts; closely combine the all-people defense posture with the people's security posture. Increase investment resources in building material foundations, equipment and weapons for national defense - security... Continue to adjust the strategic layout; perfecting plans to protect national security and territorial sovereignty, proactively having plans to respond, prevent and repel from afar, and actively prepare forces to ensure victory when bad situations happen. Formulate and effectively implement plans to prevent riots, disturbances and terrorism; plans to ensure political security, ideological - cultural security, economic security, information security, especially network security. Timely detecting and disabling the bases of reactionary organizations, definitively solving complex cases at the bases, not letting them spread to become hotspots of security and order. Continue to build the people's army, the revolutionary, regular and elite people's police force to step by step modernize, in which, there are a number of forces going straight to modernity; must build a political army first, focusing on improving political bravery, quality and capacity of cadres and soldiers; actively fight to defeat all conspiracies and tricks in the war.

Fifthly, building our Party is really clean and strong. The leadership of the Party is a decisive factor for the process of promoting the potential and strength of the Vietnamese people. Faced with new requirements, it is required that the Party constantly improve its leadership capacity and combat strength, regularly renew itself, self-correct, self-criticize, strengthen solidarity, unify and resolutely fight the opportunistic elements. Especially, focus on implementing the Resolution of the 4th Party Central Committee, term XII on strengthening Party building and rectification; prevent and reverse the deterioration of political ideology, morality, lifestyle, internal “self-evolution” and “self-transformation” manifestations, associated with effective implementation of Directive 05- Program/TW of the 12th Politburo on promoting study and following Ho Chi Minh's thought, morality. Well implement the principles in the organization and operation of the Party, especially the principle of democratic centralism; to build a really strong political, ideological, organizational and ethical level of committees and branches, serving as a basis for training, fostering and closely and comprehensively managing cadres and party members. Closely combine self-criticism and criticism within the Party with the public's criticism of the party organization, cadres and party members; always listen to suggestions and seriously absorb and correct limitations and shortcomings.

Conclusion

More than any other nation in the world, the Vietnamese people understand the pricelessness of independence and freedom. Because, in order to have peace, independence and freedom like today, our nation had to trade with the lives, blood and tears of generations of Vietnamese people. It is a voluntary sacrifice for a true goal, a noble ideal, a patriotic act of a heroic nation, a shining symbol of revolutionary heroism. It is the aspiration, will, bravery and wisdom that have created the great strength of Vietnamese people in the cause of fighting for and maintaining the independence and freedom of the Fatherland. During the process of leading the revolutionary cause, our Party and President Ho Chi Minh have highly promoted the human factor, creating great power, which is decisive for all victories of the Vietnamese revolution. Currently, in the new conditions, it is necessary to continue to deeply grasp and creatively apply Ho Chi Minh's thought on promoting the human factor to make the tradition, bravery, mettle and intelligence of the Vietnamese people become a great power to firmly defend the independence and freedom of the Fatherland.

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Author Information

Dr. Nguyen Minh Tri

Politics and National Defense Education Center Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology (HUTECH), Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Dinh The Hoang

Faculty of Philosophy, The University of Social Sciences and Humanities, Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Nguyen Van Bung

Ho Chi Minh City University of Fine Arts, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
